

Practical Care on Fruit Trees in Agroforestry Systems

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Mechanical protection of young seedlings is essential when establishing an agroforestry system

Practical care on fruit trees in agroforestry systems begins with their appropriate selection. This involves considerations of the intensity of possible care and the intended use of the harvest. In agroforestry systems utilizing fruit trees, we select species that are well adapted to the given soil-climatic area and are less demanding in terms of additional care. On grasslands, these are species that can tolerate grass cover when mature. In the case of silvopastoral use, they can coexist with livestock and also with wild animals in the open countryside, which currently cause significant economic damage. When planting fruit trees near arable land, we consider to what extent it is possible to synchronize the management of arable land with the harvest of fruits to avoid mutual conflicts. The implementation of care is preceded by a care plan. The actual care can be divided into two groups of measures. The first consists of less specialized, routine maintenance, primarily involving regular monitoring of the trees (stabilizing the tree with support in the first years, functionality of mechanical protection, occurrence of damage and diseases), mowing the undergrowth, irrigation in the first years after planting, or during critically dry periods, mulching with mulch material, applying nutrition, and applying protection after consultation. The second group of measures requires more professional preparation and focuses mainly on pruning trees, fertilization plans, and proposals for protection against specific biotic and abiotic factors.

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